

Engineering defect clustering in diamond-based materials for technological applications via quantum-mechanical descriptors

Supplemental Material

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I. GENERALISED BAND GAP AS A FUNCTION OF THE DEFECT CONCENTRATION

Generalised band gaps as a function of the defect concentration for all the defects are reported in Figure 1.

II. ELECTRONIC BAND STRUCTURES AT 1.85 % CONCENTRATION

We report the electronic band structures calculated along the standard [1] piece-wise linear path joining the high-symmetry points in the irreducible Brillouin zone of the face-centred cubic lattice. We also report the band dispersion of the structures doped with a single dopant atom for comparison [2]. Each figure corresponds to the single defect type: Figure 2 X, Figure 3 X-V, Figure 4 X-X, Figure 5 X-C-X and Figure 6 X-V-X.

FIG. 1. Generalised band gap as a function of the (a) X-V, (b) X-X, (c) X-C-X, (d) X-V-X defect concentration.

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FIG. 2. Electronic band structure of the (a) pure diamond, (b) Al-, (c) B-, (d) N-, (e) P- and (f) Si-X structures doped in 1.85 % concentration [2]. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

FIG. 3. Electronic band structure of the (a) pure diamond, (b) Al-, (c) B-, (d) N-, (e) P- and (f) Si-X-V structures doped in 1.85 % concentration. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

FIG. 4. Electronic band structure of the (a) pure diamond, (b) Al-, (c) B-, (d) N-, (e) P- and (f) Si-X-X structures doped in 1.85 % concentration. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

FIG. 5. Electronic band structure of the (a) pure diamond, (b) Al-, (c) B-, (d) N-, (e) P- and (f) Si-X-C-X structures doped in 1.85 % concentration. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

FIG. 6. Electronic band structure of the (a) pure diamond, (b) Al-, (c) B-, (d) N-, (e) P- and (f) Si-X-V-X structures doped in 1.85 % concentration. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

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